

Effects of Hydrostatic Pressure on the Mechanical Behavior of Nylon 6-Glass Fiber Composites

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ABSTRACT

The tensile, compressive, and shearing stress-strain behavior of glass fiber reinforced Nylon 6 has been investigated at high hydrostatic pressures up to 6 kbars. The glass fibers (Owens Corning "E" Glass Fiber) were copped, coated with organosilane, and randomly oriented in the polymer matrix (Allied Corp., Capron Nylon 8233). The composite contains 30% fibers by weight. Samples of the composite material were compression molded at 2 Kbar pressure and 238°C after heating to 302°C and were carefully machined to be suitable for tension, compression, and torsional shear tests.

The tests were carried out in two separate high pressure equipments, namely tension-compression test apparatus and shear test apparatus which are described elsewhere in detail (1,2). A sample was placed in the high pressure cavity of the test apparatus pressure increased to the desired intensity viz., atm., 1,2,3, 4,5, and 6 Kbar, a load or torque applied at a quasi-static speed to the specimen and stress-strain data obtained. At least three tests were carried out at each pressure. The pressure medium used was a mixture of five parts kerosene and one of Exxon's Teresstic oil.

The tensile stress-strain curves obtained at various pressures show the Young's modulus, the yield and the tensile strength, and the fracture strain all increased with increasing pressure with an exception that the fracture strain at 6 Kb deviated from the trend. Fracture mode of the samples changed from a tensile mode at low pressures (up to 2 Kbar) to a shear mode at higher pressures (3-6 Kb).

Scanning electron microscopy of the fracture surface of these tensile samples indicates that the tensile fracture at low pressures was accompanied by fractures in interfaces between the fibers and the matrix as pulled-out fibers are clearly visible and that the shear fracture was due to matrix failure and no dewetting of fibers appears to occur.

The results of compressive tests at various pressures also show that the compressive modulus and the compressive yield strength (2% off-set) increased with increasing pressure. All samples deformed beyond 20% strain without fracture. The mode of the permanent deformation changed from barreling at lower

pressures to kinking at higher pressures.

The torque-the angle of twist curves were obtained on solid cylindrical samples at various pressures. These were then converted to the maximum shear stress - the maximum shear strain curves. The shear modulus and the shear yield stress were found to be an increasing function of pressure. However, the shear fracture strain increased overall, though nonuniformly, with increasing pressure. A transition from a tensile mode of fracture at lower pressure to a shear mode at higher pressures was observed to occur between 3 to 4 Kbar. The increase in the fracture strain appears to be associated with the change in the fracture mode.

A three-dimensional model has been proposed to explain the pressure dependent properties which were observed on the randomly oriented, chopped fiber composites, taking into consideration the changes in volume fraction of fibers due to applied pressure, the increase in matrix strength with increasing pressure, and the increase in interfacial shear stress with increasing pressure.

- (1) A. A. Silano and K. D. Pae, Rev. Sci. Instr., 48, 307 (1977).
- (2) D. L. Questad, K. D. Pae, B. A. Newman and J. I. Scheinbeim, J. Appl. Phy., 51, 5100 (1980).